

THE IMPORTANCE OF PUBLIC TRANSPORT FOR PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES**Marija Stojanoska****Vaska Atanasova****Nikola Krstanoski**

Faculty of Technical Sciences

North Macedonia

Makedonska Falanga 37, Bitola, 7000

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14277120>**Abstract**

The city is an environment where people live, work, get educated, hang out, have fun, use various services. From the point of view of urban planners, this means that the city must provide all these functions in a defined space with optimal planning of the appropriate land use. Of course, in order for all this to work, it is necessary to ensure the adequate mobility of the population. A person has a large number of rights, one of the basic ones being the right to mobility. All human mobilities are realized on completely or partially arranged traffic surfaces, but what about people who have certain disabilities, how will they achieve their mobility. The real integration of people with disabilities into the overall living starts with providing them with conditions for smooth communication and movement. The way in which they will achieve their mobility depends on the offered variants of means of transportation, people do not always own their own car, so they are forced to use another alternative means, such as public city transportation. In this paper, the mobility of this group of people will be analyzed, with public transport in the territory of the city of Bitola.

Keywords: transportation, travelers, disability, mobility, survey.

Introduction

People with more severe physical disabilities, especially people who move exclusively with a wheelchair, are forced to use their own car or taxi transportation to go to work every day, to the doctor, to the store, to the market, to various cultural and sports events, to participate in the activities of their associations, to visit relatives and friends, for a walk... Simply, wherever they need to move, because they have no other alternative. They cannot ride a bicycle, they cannot use public transportation, because it is either not organized in their local governments, or is not adapted for the transport of passengers in wheelchairs, and they cannot even walk. Because of this, their living costs are significantly higher compared to people who do not face some kind of disability.

Public transportation of passengers and goods is transportation that is available to all users under equal conditions. Public urban transport services are an important aspect of any urban transport system, providing mobility for a large number of passengers to different destinations in different directions and at the same time through one transport facility. Public city transport should offer the following quality conditions: safety, reliability, reduction of congestion, economy, ecologically oriented towards the environment, social integration, faster, greater number of lines and frequency of movement. Public transport in Bitola is carried out by 5 licensed private operators. The current public transport service in the city's metropolitan area is represented by 5 urban lines. Public transportation in Bitola is carried out only by circular routes.

A survey was conducted on the territory of the city of Bitola for the users of public city transports, the survey was conducted in a public transport vehicle and electronically. The target group who responded to the

survey was 315 users. Here, the quality of services offered by public city transport was analyzed, as well as the satisfaction of the needs of persons with disabilities.

Disabled people in Macedonia

Persons with disabilities in the Republic of Macedonia encounter various barriers when performing everyday activities: entering and using residential and public buildings, public transport, using services and products. The law on transportation in passenger traffic does not provide a formal and essential equality of disabled citizens. On the other hand, it provides benefits for preferential transport, namely disabled persons, ie blind persons with impairment over 90%, as well as a disabled person with a physical disability of 100% together with his companion are exempt from paying a ticket in both directions of movement.

Additionally the legislator determines: the technical regulations on who should drive the vehicle, the authorized institutions for issuing the special sign, providing the benefit of toll exemption for persons with disabilities defined by diagnosis and percentage of disability. This provision puts people with disabilities at a disadvantage and limits the right to association, which leads to discrimination within the group of people with disabilities. On the other hand, the legislator, instead of enabling persons with disabilities to enjoy the right to transportation/mobility based on the principle of non-discrimination and equality, provides a financial benefit that covers only a certain number of persons with disability who in turn must be members of traditional organizations of persons with disability.

In the provisions of these laws, the principle of accessibility and affordability are not mentioned in the conditions for obtaining a permit and license of buses, trains or auto-taxi transportation, in order to meet at least the minimum conditions for providing transportation for passengers with disabilities. On the other hand,

the deficiency in the regulation of parking spaces in the Law on Traffic Safety is the failure to define what constitutes a parking space for persons with disabilities, as well as the failure to define the content and appearance of the special sign that should be placed on vehicles for persons with disabilities. All these deficiencies negatively affect these persons and their choice of mode of transportation.

A total of 94,412 people with disabilities live in the country, according to the latest data from the census carried out by the State Statistics Office in 2021 year. The majority of people with disabilities are women (52,203), and the majority of these people, that is, over 40 percent, have problems with movement. There are 1,674 children with disabilities aged 0 to 14 in the country, 43.5 percent are people aged 15 to 64, and 54.8 percent are 65 and older. In the census, apart from problems with movement, 12,371 declared that they have problems with sight, 5,947 with hearing, 3,896 with communication, and even 33,699 people declared that they have other difficulties.

Public city transport and meeting the needs of disabled people

In Macedonia, a more developed (albeit problematic) public urban transport system is found in the capital Skopje. In the last decade, there has been a trend towards the renewal or introduction for the first time of public urban transport in smaller towns in Macedonia.

Public urban transport has been introduced in Prilep, Ohrid, Kavadarci, Tetovo, Kocani, Kumanovo, Veles, and initiatives are underway to introduce public transport in Strumica, Shtip and other smaller towns.

Public city transport should be accessible to all, to enable mobility of all users of the service, safety, reliability and quality of service at affordable prices. When it comes to people with disabilities, different measures are introduced to facilitate their mobility.

In 2010, the city of Skopje put into use for the first time the new vehicle adapted to the physically disabled. The number of users and their needs are increasing day by day, and therefore it is necessary to increase the number of vehicles that will go along organized routes and will cover the optimal number of users. In 2016, the number of such vehicles reached 4. The transportation of these persons was carried out with three specially adapted vehicles, one minibus and one bus with an automatically operated ramp for a wheelchair and other equipment that ensures the safety of users. The transport is well organized because it is realized on the basis of telephone calls, according to which the driving schedule is made. The transportation is agreed on working days, and for better planning it is recommended to do it on the previous working day and the scheduling of the transportation is agreed with a phone call according to the principle of order of appointment. Figure 1 shows a public urban transport vehicle modeled for people with disabilities.

Fig.1 Shows a public urban transport vehicle modeled for people with disabilities

In 2019, the city of Prilep received four ecological methane vehicles. The vehicles are modernly equipped, 12 meters long, double-winged, with 27 seats, with a ramp for passengers with wheelchairs, that is, they have the capacity to transport 78 passengers standing.

As part of the celebration of the European Mobility Week in 2022, the citizens of Prilep had the opportunity to ride the electric bus as a regular city line and get to know the advantages offered by electric public transport: environmentally friendly, smart, safe and

comfortable buses, with 0 emission of harmful gases, low noise levels and low operating costs, but also public city transport accessible to people with disabilities. These vehicles have stickers that indicate that the vehicle is equipped with additional equipment to meet the needs of disabled people. This means that all persons with disabilities will be able to meet their mobility needs with these vehicles. Figure 2 shows the ramp in a public city transport vehicle, which enables fast and safe entry and exit of passengers from the vehicle.

Fig.2 Show the ramp in a public city transport vehicle

Figure 3 shows the information markings on the vehicle itself, that it can carry disabled persons.

Fig.3 Show the information markings on the vehicle itself, that it can carry disabled persons

In the vehicle of public city transport there is a special space where people with disabilities can be transported, that place is marked with yellow color and sticker. Also, for persons with partial disabilities, i.e.

those who move with a cane, they will be able to sit on those chairs that are not very far from the entrance / exit door. This is shown in figure 4.

Fig.4 Location of persons with disabilities in the vehicle of public transport

Permits for the transportation of passengers in the territory of the city of Bitola were granted for the first time in 2010, to 9 (nine) carriers and 19 lines. But with the passage of time and due to a number of problems and shortcomings, today public city transport in Bitola is provided by 5 licensed private operators. The current

public transport service in the city's metropolitan area is represented by 5 urban lines. Public transportation in Bitola is carried out only by circular routes. As a consequence, the current situation is characterized by an unstable service of public transport. Figure 5 shows a public transport vehicle in Bitola.

Fig.5 Public transport vehicle in Bitola

One of the most used and strongest methods of market research is a survey. Surveys are the most widely used because they are the easiest to conduct and the simplest to collect information that still arrives in a form that is easy to analyze. In order to understand the shortcomings and the quality of the services offered by the public city transport in Bitola, a survey was conducted electronically and in the vehicle itself, where 315 users were included. In this survey, people with

disabilities were included, that is, whether public city transport meets their needs.

First, let's look at the survey question on how often you use public transport in Bitola. We can see from the tabular presentation that most of the respondents regularly use the public city transport, i.e. 145 (46%), often 65 or 20.6%, sometimes 62 or 19.7%, while rarely 11.4% and never very few respondents, or only 2.2%. This is shown in Table 1.

T.1 Analysis of the frequency of use of public city transportation

How often do you use public urban passenger transportation?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Regularly	145	46,0	46,0	46,0
	Often	65	20,6	20,6	66,7
	Sometimes	62	19,7	19,7	86,3
	Rarely	36	11,4	11,4	97,8
	Never	7	2,2	2,2	100,0
	Total	315	100,0	100,0	

Source: Created by the authors

From the conducted survey, we can conclude that the quality of public city transport in Bitola is good, that is, 181 respondents or 57.5% gave that answer. While

the percentage of excellent or very bad is very small. We can see this in table 2.

T.2 Quality of public urban passenger transport

Quality of public urban passenger transport					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Excellent	26	8,3	8,3	8,3
	Very good	40	12,7	12,7	21,0
	Good	181	57,5	57,5	78,4
	Bad	51	16,2	16,2	94,6
	Very bad	17	5,4	5,4	100,0
	Total	315	100,0	100,0	

Source: Created by the authors

There are a number of reasons why the citizens of the city of Bitola do not use the services of public transport, first dirty buses, bad and irregular timetables, too much crowding, lack of information, but also the lack of adequate equipment and devices for the mobility of people with disabilities. Table 3 shows the results of the survey conducted on the question of whether

public urban transport meets the needs of people with disabilities. We can conclude that the public transport vehicles do not meet the needs of people with disabilities, as 156 or 49.5% of the respondents consider this, and 124 or 39.4% partially agree. While 35 respondents, or 11.1%, answered with yes.

T.3 Meeting the needs of mobility with public city transport of persons with disabilities

As a user of the services of public city transport, do you think that it meets the needs of people with disabilities					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	35	11,1	11,1	11,1
	Partially	124	39,4	39,4	50,5
	No	156	49,5	49,5	100,0
	Total	315	100,0	100,0	

Source: Created by the authors

Conclusion

Transportation is essential for people of all ages and backgrounds to live a fulfilling and satisfying life. Public transport (PT) can facilitate access to the community and improve social participation. However, people with disabilities may encounter barriers or facilitators in the entire travel chain that can lead to negative or positive perceptions in terms of self-efficacy or satisfaction. Planning a journey, knowing the waiting times at bus stops, knowing where to get off, taking correct action in the case of disruption—using public transport requires having access to information at every step along the way. The task, of course, is far more complicated for people living with a disability, whether motor, sensory or intellectual. From the paper, we can conclude that the need for mobility should be met for all citizens, regardless of the obstacles they face. Vehicles must be equipped with devices for safe entry/exit of passengers, ramps, a special place in the vehicle, exemption from paying a ticket, access to stands, access to information. It is necessary to enter an account for the future of:

“accessibility” in a broader sense – it concerns not only those registered as disabled but those with any kind of impairment, whether permanent or temporary.

Ensure collaboration for integrated transport and urban planning to design accessible door-to-door routes.

Use public campaigns to improve social attitudes and transport etiquette towards persons with disabilities and access needs.

Make the participation of disability/accessibility experts mandatory for the development of standards for vehicles, mobility systems and transport services.

Coordinate urban public transport with suburban and regional transport to provide smooth transitions for travellers with and without disabilities. In the long run, investments in the transport infrastructure are needed.

Infrastructural barriers are the most limiting barriers as they often make independent travel impossible.

While assistive equipment can help mitigate inaccessible design, the removal of structural barriers is crucial in the long-term.

References:

1. <http://www.mobilnost.mk/index.php/2011-10-26-09-10-24/394>
2. https://civicamobilitas.mk/wp-content/uploads/2018/02/0._holisticki_izvestaj_za_licata_so_poprecenost_vo_makedonija-mk.pdf
3. <https://skopjeinfo.mk/prevozot-za-lica-so-telesna-invalidnost-kje-se-zakazhuvava-telefonski>
4. <https://vistinomer.mk/popisot-otkri-kolkulugje-so-poprechenost-zhiveat-vo-opshtinite-na-red-se-gradonachalnicite-da-im-obezbedat-uslovi/>
5. https://cms.mtsp.gov.mk/mart-2014-ns_article-se-ovozmozuvava-besplatno-prevoz-za-potpolnogluvite-lica-i-lica-so-intelektualna-poprecenost.nsp
6. <https://nezavisen.mk/povlasteni-bileti-za-jsp-za-lica-so-poprechenost-izglasano-novi-avtobusi-i-brt-sistem-ne/>
7. <https://www.prilep.gov.mk/pred-prilepchani-prezentiran-novociti-volt-novoto-ekonomichno-i-ekoloshko-reshenie-za-urban-transport/>
8. <https://inovativnost.mk/2019/08/24/%D0%BF%D1%80%D0%B8%D0%BB%D0%B5%D0%BF-%D0%B2%D0%BE%D0%B2%D0%B5%D0%B4%D0%B5-%D0%B3%D1%80%D0%B0%D0%B4%D1%81%D0%BA%D0%B8-%D0%B0%D0%B2%D1%82%D0%BE%D0%B1%D1%83%D1%81%D0%B8-%D0%BD%D0%B0-%D0%BC%D0%B5%D1%82/>
9. <https://www.uitp.org/news/how-to-make-public-transport-accessible-and-inclusive-for-all/>
10. https://bitola.info/mk/vozen_red_opstinski_liniski_prevoz/